

Exploring Clinical Outcomes of Tenecteplase Induced Thrombolysis in ST-Elevation Myocardial Infarction: A Cross-Sectional Analysis at Government General Hospital, Kurnool

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Abstract

The main aim & objective of our study was to determine the safety and effectiveness of Tenecteplase (TNK) among patients with a diagnosis of ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) undergoing thrombolytic therapy. The study took place at the Government General Hospital Kurnool, and total 141 subjects were included who were aged 20-80 years and had an ECG displaying a diagnosis of STEMI less than 12 hours after the emergence of symptoms. Our research revealed the male prevalence and the average age of patients was 52.6 years. AAMI was the most common subtype with 55.3 percent. The ST-segment elevation had significantly reduced in response to thrombolytic therapy with Tenecteplase, which implied that myocardial reperfusion was successful. The Numerical Pain Rating Scale (NPRS) rating decreased to 0 which shows the complete absence of the ischemic chest pain in the majority of patients. There were few adverse events with tenecteplase and this shows that the drug has good safety profile. Our research findings endorse the application of Tenecteplase as a primary thrombolytic agent in pharmacoinvasive management of STEMI especially in resource-restrained models. Its proven effectiveness, good safety profile and convenience of administration make it an effective and viable alternative to consider in an environment where access to percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) is constrained by time.

Keywords: Tenecteplase, ST Elevation Myocardial Infarction (STEMI), Anterior wall myocardial infarction (AAMI), Numerical Pain Rating Scale (NPRS), Naranjo's Scale.

Introduction

ST-Elevation Myocardial Infarction (STEMI) is a form of acute myocardial infarction that occurs because of complete blockage of a coronary artery resulting in extended ischemia and death of myocardial cells. It is marked by continuous ST-segment elevation in an electrocardiogram (ECG) and cardiac biomarkers, which implies that the heart muscle has suffered significant damage^{1,2}. ST-Elevation Myocardial Infarction (STEMI) continues to be a significant source of morbidity and mortality in all countries, including those with high incomes, although it has decreased in recent decades because of better prevention, earlier diagnosis, and treatment of cardiovascular risk factors. In the U.S., STEMI causes 25-40 percent of all myocardial infarctions and the rest are non-ST-elevation myocardial infarctions.³ cardiovascular diseases inclusive of STEMI cause estimated 17.9 million deaths each year across the globe with a heavy burden in low and middle-income nations where accessibility to timely reperfusion treatment is scarce. Regardless of improved treatment, STEMI remains linked with high in-hospital mortality rates, especially among older adults and those with

comorbidities, which highlights the need to focus on interventions in the area of STEMI related to the reduction of disparities in care and outcomes.⁴ ST-Elevation Myocardial Infarction (STEMI) aetiology is mainly associated with the rupture or erosion of an atherosclerotic plaque within a coronary artery, and the development of a thrombus that entirely obstructs blood flow, resulting in myocardial ischemia and necrosis.⁵

The Atherosclerosis progresses over time when lipids and inflammatory cells plus fibrous components are deposited on the wall of the arteries. A combination of both the modifiable and non-modifiable risk factors is very strong in influencing this pathophysiological process. Smoking, high levels of low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol, diabetes mellitus, physical inactivity, and poor diet are major modifiable risk factors, which contribute significantly to the onset and progression of the coronary artery disease thus increase the risk of developing STEMI.^{6,7,8} The main pathophysiological cause of STEMI is often caused by a ruptured atherosclerotic plaque and the formation of a thrombus. The disease causes infarction and transmural myocardial ischemia. The pathogenesis of atherosclerosis starts with injury of endothelium, lipids infiltration, and chronic inflammation.^{9,10} This eventually develops into a vulnerable plaque with its large lipid core and thin fibrous cap prone to rupture or erosion with mechanical forces or inflammation leaving the highly thrombogenic core with lipids and tissue factor accessible to circulating blood. It results into a rapid platelet activation, aggregation, and coagulation cascade initiation.¹¹ The platelet thrombus formed at the rupture site can become complete within a short time, thus causing complete occlusion of the coronary artery and abrupt cessation of delivery of oxygen to the downstream myocardial tissue, leading to ischemic metabolism in the affected myocardium resulting in lactic acidosis, an ion pump dysfunction, calcium overload, and eventual death of the affected myocardium^{12,13} as reopening the artery via PCI or thrombolysis may result in additional injury termed reperfusion injury due to oxidative stress, inflammation, and mitochondrial dysfunction.¹⁴ Myocardial infarction manifested by chest pains, which may extend to the arms, back, neck or jaw, with or without shortness of breath, nausea or diaphoresis are the typical presentations of STEMI¹⁵. STEMI is tested as a result of a two or more contiguous leads of ≥ 1 mm of ST-segment elevation that is typically ≥ 2 mm in all other leads except V2-V3 with ≥ 40 years, ≥ 2.5 mm in men less than 40 years, or ≥ 1.5 mm in women.¹⁵ The Preferred biomarkers of myocardial injury are cardiac troponins which are required to confirm the diagnosis, but choice of treatment is largely ECG-driven in STEMI.¹⁶ The imaging studies such as echocardiography or coronary angiography may be used to detect wall motion abnormalities or coronary occlusion.¹⁷

The management of STEMI includes lifestyle modifications such as smoking cessation, weight management, exercise, and dietary changes.¹⁸ The pharmacotherapy involves the use of clopidogrel, ticagrelor and Nitrates either sublingual or IV, Morphine if there is persistence of chest pain, Beta-blockers when there are no contraindications. Aspirin and a P2Y12 inhibitor is recommended as soon as possible with additional oxygen used in situations of hypoxemia when SaO₂ <90%.¹⁹ The Reperfusion Therapy includes Primary PCI and Fibrinolytic Therapy which is Given when PCI is unavailable within 120 minutes of FMC and within 30 minutes of hospital arrival.¹⁷ A dual antiplatelet therapy which includes Aspirin + P2Y12 inhibitor should be continued for at least 12 months along with Anticoagulants like unfractionated heparin, or enoxaparin or bivalirudin, in STEMI patients undergoing PCI if there is no contraindications.²⁰ Statins such as atorvastatin 80 mg/kg/day should be given and ACE inhibitors or ARBs particularly in patients with an EF less than 40 percent or anterior MI and Beta-blockers reduce the mortality and reinfarction and Aldosterone antagonists should give in STEMI patients if EF is less than 40% and with symptoms of heart failure.²⁰

2. Aim & Objective

The main aim & objectives of our study is to evaluate the safety and Efficacy of Tenecteplase in ST-segment elevated myocardial infraction patients undergoing Thrombolysis.

3. Methodology

Study Design

Cross Sectional observation study.

Study Duration & Study Site

A six-months observational study was undertaken at the Department of Cardiology, Government General Hospital, Kurnool, during which 141 eligible patients were enrolled for analysis.

Collection of Data

Data collection is done by using the following Annexures.

Annexure-1 (Patient Demographic Data Collection Form), Annexure-2 (Numeric pain rating scale), Annexure-3 (Naranjo's Scale)

Patient Selection

Inclusion Criteria

- All patients prescribed with Tenecteplase.
- Patients between age group of 20- 80years.
- Patients who are diagnosed with STEMI based on clinical symptoms and ECG.
- Patients undergoing thrombolytic therapy within 12 hours from the onset of ischemic chest pain.
- Patients with co-morbidities who are prescribed with Tenecteplase.
- Patients who are willing to participate in study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patient with age less than 20 years.
- Patient with prior history of coronary artery disease.
- Patient with prior history of stroke.
- Delayed presentation of patient i.e. greater than 12 hours.
- Patient with hypertensive emergency and urgency condition.
- Patient with major trauma within 3 months.
- Patients with prior treatment of anticoagulant therapy.
- Pregnancy and lactating women's and all the patients who are not willing to participate in our study. And the further results were evaluated using MS. Excel, Wilcoxon sign rank test, chi-square test.

4. Results

4.1 Gender Wise Distribution of Subjects

A total of 141 subjects were collected among them 114 are males and 27 are females.

Table 4.1: Gender Wise Distribution of Subjects

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Female	27	19.1
Male	114	80.9
Total	141	100

Figure 4.1: Gender Wise Distribution of Subjects

4.2 Age Wise Distribution of Subjects

A total number of 141 subjects were collected among them the age of distribution was as follows 18-40 are (30), 40-60 are (72) and above 60 are (39). Mean age among 141 subjects is 52.67 ± 13.39 .

Table 4.2 Age Wise Distribution of Subjects

Age	Frequency	Percentage
<40 years	30	21.3
40-60 years	72	51.1
>60 years	39	27.7
Total	141	100
Mean age	52.67 ± 13.39	

Figure 4.2: Age Wise Distribution of Subjects

4.3 Distribution of Subjects Based on Martial Status

A total 141 subjects among them 129 were Married, 8 were consanguineous married, and 4 were unmarried.

Table 4.3 Based on Martial Status

Marital status	Frequency	Percentage
Consanguineous married	8	5.7
Married	129	91.5
Unmarried	4	2.8
Total	141	100

Figure 4.3: Distribution Based on Martial Status

4.4 Distribution of Subjects Based on Education Status

Among 141 subjects 113 were illiterate and 28 were literate.

Table 4.4 Based on Education Status

Educational status	Frequency	Percentage
Illiterate	113	80.1
Literate	28	19.9
Total	141	100

Figure 4.4: Based On Education Status

4.5 Distribution of Subjects Based on Social Habits

A total number of 141 subjects were collected, among them 57 were both smokers, alcoholic followed by 54 were no reported habits, 16 were smokers, 9 were alcoholic.

Table 4.5 Distribution of Subjects Based on Social Habits

SOCIAL HABITS	Frequency	Percentage
Smoking	16	11.3
Smoking, Alcoholic	57	40.4
Smoking, Alcoholic, Tobacco	3	2.1
Alcoholic	9	6.4
Tobacco, Alcoholic	1	0.7
Tobacco	1	0.7
No	54	38.3
Total	141	100

Figure 4.5: Based On Social Habits

4.6 Distribution of Subjects Based on Co-Morbid Conditions

Out of 141 subjects, individuals without conventional risk factors (66) exhibit the highest susceptibility to myocardial infarction (MI), followed by those with hypertension (32), individuals with concurrent hypertension, family history and diabetes mellitus (18), and those with hypertension, family history (15) and diabetes mellitus (10) alone.

Table 4.6: Distribution of Subjects Based on Co-Morbid Conditions

Co morbidities	Frequency	Percentage
HTN	32	22.7
HTN, Family history	15	10.6
HTN, DM, Family history	18	12.8
DM	10	7.1
NO Risk Factors	66	46.8

Figure 4.6: Distribution of Subjects Based on Co-Morbid Conditions

4.7 Distribution of Subjects Based on Type of MI

In our research study ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) is classified based on ECG findings, The most prevalent was anterior wall myocardial infarction (AWMI) 78, followed by inferior wall myocardial infarction (IWMI) with posterior wall myocardial infarction (PWMI) (28) The third most common was IWMI alone 15 and 11 were IWMI+PWMI+RVMI while the least frequent presentation was IWMI with right ventricular myocardial infarction (RWMI).

Table 4.7: Distribution of Subjects Based on Type of MI

Type of MI	Frequency	Percentage
AWMI	78	55.3
IWMI	15	10.6
IWMI+PWMI	28	19.9
IWMI+PWMI+RVMI	11	7.8
IWMI+RVMI	9	6.4
Total	141	100

Figure 4.7: Distribution of Subjects Based on Type of MI

4.8 Distribution of Subjects Based on Kilip Classification

Out of 141 subjects, 122 were in class 1, 14 were in class 2, 3 were in class 3, and 2 were in class 4.

Table 4.8: Distribution of Subjects Based on KILIP Classification

KILIP classification	Frequency	Percentage
I	122	86.5
II	14	9.9
III	3	2.1
IV	2	1.4
Total	141	100

Figure 4.8: Distribution of Subjects Based on KILIP Classification

4.9 Distribution of Subjects Based on Ejection Fraction

Among the 141 subjects, 90 had mild ejection fraction, 37 had moderate, 12 had normal, and 2 had severe ejection fraction.

Table 4.9: Distribution of Subjects Based on Ejection Fraction

EJECTION FRACTION	Frequency	Percentage
Normal	12	8.5
Mild	90	63.8
Moderate	37	26.2
Severe	2	1.4
Total	141	100

Figure 4.9: Distribution of Subjects Based on Ejection Fraction

4.10 Distribution of Subjects Based on Lipid Profile

Based on Total Cholesterol level out of 141 subjects, 106 had low total cholesterol levels, 20 had high levels and 15 were in the borderline range and 98 had acceptable HDL levels, 32 had low HDL levels, and 11 had high HDL levels and 32 had high LDL, 32 had very high LDL, 28 had low LDL, 27 were in the borderline high range, and 22 had acceptable LDL levels and 73 had low levels, 46 had borderline high levels, 12 had high levels, and 10 had very high levels.

Table 4.10: Distribution of Subjects Based on Lipid Profile

Total Cholesterol	Frequency	Percentage
Low	106	75.2
Borderline High	15	10.6
High	20	14.2
HDL	Frequency	Percentage
Low	32	22.7
Acceptable	98	69.5
High	11	7.8
LDL	Frequency	Percentage
Acceptable	22	15.6
Low	28	19.9
Borderline High	27	19.1
High	32	22.7
Very High	32	22.7
Triglycerides	Frequency	Percentage
Low	73	51.8
Borderline High	46	32.6
High	12	8.5
Very High	10	7.1

Figure 4.10: Distribution of Subjects Based on Lipid Profile

4.11 Distribution of Subjects Based on Numeric Pain Rating Scale

4.11.1 Distribution of Subjects Based on Numeric Pain Rating Scale (Pre-Elaxim)

Based on the Numeric Pain Rating Scale before Elaxim, among 141 subjects, 130 experienced severe pain, 6 had moderate pain, and 5 reported the worst pain.

Table 4.11.1 Distribution of subjects based on Numeric pain rating scale (pre-Elaxim)

Pre Elaxim	Frequency	Percentage
Moderate	6	4.3
Severe	130	92.2
Worst	5	3.5

Figure 4.11.1 Distribution of subjects based on Numeric pain rating scale (pre-Elaxim)

4.11.2 Distribution of Subjects Based on Numeric Pain Rating Scale (Post Elaxim)

After Elaxim administration, among 141 subjects, 78 reported no pain, 61 reported mild pain, and 2 reported moderate pain based on the Numeric Pain Rating Scale.

Table 4.11.2 Distribution of subjects based on Numeric Pain Rating Scale (Post-Elaxim)

Post ELAXIM	Frequency	Percentage
No Pain	78	55.3
Mild	61	43.3
Moderate	2	1.4

Figure 4.11.2: Distribution of subjects based on Numeric Pain Rating Scale (Post-Elaxim)

4.12 Comparison of subjects before and after Tenecteplase by NPRS using Chi-square test

In our 141-patient study, we used the Numeric Pain Scale to quantify pain levels and analyzed the results using the Chi-square test.

Prior to the administration of tenecteplase, 130 individuals reported significant pain. Following therapy, 72 patients reported no discomfort, 58 reported mild pain, and six reported serious pain. Among those who experienced moderate pain prior to tenecteplase, four experienced no discomfort following therapy, one reported mild pain, and one remained in moderate pain. Of the patients who initially suffered the most pain, two reported no discomfort after therapy, two improved to mild pain, and one improved to moderate pain.

TABLE 4.12 Comparison of Subjects Before and After Tenecteplase by NPRS Using Chi-Square Test

Pre Elaxim	Post Elaxim			Total	Chi-Square P value
	No pain	Mild	Moderate		
Moderate	4 (66.7)	1 (16.7)	1 (16.7)	6	25.250 <0.001
Severe	72 (55.4)	58 (44.6)	0 (0)	130	
Worst	2 (40)	2 (40)	1 (20)	5	
Total	78 (55.3)	61 (43.3)	2 (1.4)	141	

Figure 4.12 Comparison of Subjects Before and After Tenecteplase by NPRS Using Chi-Square Test

4.13 Distribution of Subjects Based on Window Period

Out of 141 subjects, 79 received tenecteplase within the window period, while 62 received it outside the window period.

Table 4.13 Distribution of Subjects Based on Window Period

Window period	Frequency	Percentage
No	62	44
Yes	79	56
Total	141	100

Figure 4.13 Distribution of Subjects Based on Window Period

4.14 Assessing Safety of Tenecteplase by Naranjo Scale

The safety of tenecteplase was assessed using the Naranjo scale. Only 2 subjects scored 9, indicating a probable adverse drug reaction, while 139 subjects scored 0, suggesting no adverse reaction.

Table 4.14: Assessing Safety of Tenecteplase by Naranjo Scale

NARANZO Scale	Frequency	Percentage
0	139	98.6
9	2	1.4
Total	141	100

Figure 4.14: Assessing Safety of Tenecteplase by Naranzo Scale

4.15 Distribution of Subjects Based on CAG Report

Among the 141 subjects, based on angiogram reports, 93 underwent PTCA (Percutaneous Transluminal Coronary Angioplasty), 37 were planned for medical management, and 11 were scheduled for CABG (Coronary Artery Bypass Grafting).

Table 4.15 Distribution of Subjects Based on CAG Report

CAG report	Frequency	Percentage
MM	37	26.2
PTCA	93	66
CABG	11	7.8

Figure 4.15 Distribution of Subjects Based on CAG Report

4.16 Comparison of ST Segment Height Before and After Tenecteplase by Wilcoxon Sign Rank Test

Among the 141 subjects, ST-segment height on ECG was compared before and after tenecteplase administration. Before tenecteplase administration, the median ST-segment height was 5 mm, with an interquartile range (IQR) of 2.5–7 mm. After tenecteplase administration, the median ST-segment height decreased to 1 mm, with an IQR of 0–2 mm. The comparison was analyzed using the Wilcoxon rank test.

TABLE 4.16 Comparison of ST Segment Height Before and After Tenecteplase By Wilcoxon Sign Rank Test

PAIRED SAMPLES STATISTICS				
		Median	Inter quartile range	Wilcoxon sign rank test (p value)
Pair	ST SEGMENT HEIGHT BEFORE TNK	5	2.5-7	9.720 <0.001
	ST SEGMENT HEIGHT AFTER TNK	1	0-2	

FIGURE 4.16 Comparison of ST Segment Height Before and After Tenecteplase by Wilcoxon Sign Rank Test

4.17 Comparison of NPRS Before and After Tenecteplase by Wilcoxon Sign Rank Test

In our study of 141 subjects, we assessed pain levels using the Numeric Pain Rating Scale (NPRS) before and after administering tenecteplase. Before treatment, most patients reported severe pain, with a median score of 9. After treatment, the majority of patients experienced significant pain relief, with the median pain score dropping to 0. The interquartile range (the middle 50% of pain scores) before treatment was 8 to 9, indicating high pain levels. After treatment, this range significantly decreased to 0 to 2, showing a large improvement in pain relief for most subjects.

We used the Wilcoxon sign-rank test to analyse the data, which confirmed that the reduction in pain was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), meaning the improvement in pain scores was highly unlikely to be due to chance. This suggests that tenecteplase was effective in reducing pain in these patients.

Table 4.17 Comparison of NPRS Before and After Tenecteplase by Wilcoxon Sign Rank Test

PAIRED SAMPLES STATISTICS				
		Median	Inter quartile range	Wilcoxon sign rank test (p value)
Pair	NPRS pre	9	8-9	10.412 <0.001
	NPRS post	0	0-2	

Figure 4.17 Comparison of NPRS Before and After Tenecteplase by Wilcoxon Sign Rank Test

4.18 Comparison of Pain Scores and ST-Segment Heights Before and After Tenecteplase by Treatment Window Period

In our study of 141 subjects, we compared pain levels and ST-segment heights on ECG before and after tenecteplase administration, separating the subjects into two groups: those treated within the window period and those treated outside the window period.

Before treatment, most subjects in both groups had high pain levels (median score of 9) and elevated ST-segment heights (median of 4.5–5 mm). After tenecteplase, pain levels dropped significantly (median score of 0), and ST-segment heights decreased to near normal (median of 0–1 mm) in both groups. The Wilcoxon sign-rank test showed that these changes were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) for both groups, indicating that tenecteplase effectively reduced pain and improved ECG results, with improvements unlikely due to chance.

Table 4.18 Comparison of Pain Scores And ST-Segment Heights Before and After Tenecteplase by Treatment Window Period

WINDOW PERIOD		Median	IQR	Wilcoxon sign rank test (p value)
NO	NPRS Pre	9	8-9	6.937
	NPRS Post	0	0-1	<0.001

	ST SEGMENT HEIGHT BEFORE TNK	4.5	2-7	6.263
	ST SEGMENT HEIGHT AFTER TNK	0	0-1	<0.001
YES	NPRS_Pre	9	8-9	7.796
	NPRS_Post	0	0-1	<0.001
	ST SEGMENT HEIGHT BEFORE TNK	5	3-7	7.448
	ST SEGMENT HEIGHT AFTER TNK	1	0-2	<0.001

Figure 4.18.1 Comparison of Pain Scores before and after Tenecteplase, by Treatment out Side the Window Period

Figure 4.18.2 Comparison of Pain Scores Before and After Tenecteplase, By Treatment within the Window Period

Figure 4.18.3 Comparison of ST-Segment Heights Before and After Tenecteplase, by Treatment outside the Window Period

Figure 4.18.4 Comparison of ST-Segment Heights Before and After Tenecteplase, By Treatment within the Window Period

5. Discussion

In our study, male patients were more commonly affected, which is consistent with the findings of Abbas Al Sharifi et al., who also reported a higher prevalence among males. Regarding age distribution, the mean age in our study was 52.6 years, compared to 54.94 years in the study by Abbas Al Sharifi et al. When examining social habits, we found that individuals who smoked and consumed alcohol were more commonly affected.

In contrast, Hari Shankar et al. reported smoking as the most common habit associated with the condition. Regarding comorbid conditions, the majority of patients in our study who were prone to STEMI did not have conventional risk factors. However, among those with comorbidities, hypertension (90 patients), diabetes mellitus (90 patients), and dyslipidaemia (90 patients) were most common. Similarly, Mahidur Rahman et al. found hypertension in 84% of patients, followed by diabetes mellitus (66%) and dyslipidaemia (36%).

In our study, the majority of patients (55.3%) presented with anterior wall myocardial infarction, which is consistent with findings from previous studies. Iyengar et al. reported a similar incidence of anterior MI at 55.01%, while S. Sameer et al. observed it in 40% of their study population.

With regard to heart failure classification at presentation, most of our patients were categorized as Killip Class I, indicating a lower degree of clinical heart failure. This observation aligns with the findings of Mahidur Rahman et al., who also reported a predominance of patients in Killip Class I.

When assessing the efficacy of Tenecteplase (TNK), we found a significant reduction in ST-segment elevation on ECG. In our study, the average ST-segment elevation prior to TNK administration was 5 mm, which decreased to 1 mm post-treatment. This indicates a substantial resolution of myocardial injury. Comparatively, in the study by Neel et al., the ST-segment elevation decreased from 3.28 mm to 1.56 mm following TNK administration. These results suggest that Tenecteplase demonstrates a high level of efficacy in myocardial reperfusion.

Another parameter supporting the effectiveness of Tenecteplase in our study was the Numeric Pain Score (NPS). Patients reported a reduction from a mean score of 9 before administration to 0 after thrombolysis, indicating complete relief of chest pain. In comparison, Neel et al.

documented a reduction in pain score from 8 to 1 post-TNK. These findings further reinforce the conclusion that Tenecteplase is a highly effective thrombolytic agent in the management of ST-elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI).

In terms of safety, our study demonstrated a low complication rate of 1.4% following Tenecteplase (TNK) administration. This is slightly lower than the 2% complication rate reported by Nik Azlan Nik Mohamad et al. in their study, which further supports the favourable safety profile of TNK in the management of STEMI.

Regarding the therapeutic window, Iyengar et al. found that Tenecteplase remained effective even when administered beyond the conventional window period. Similarly, our study also observed significant clinical improvement in patients who received TNK outside the recommended window, indicating that the drug retains its efficacy even when thrombolysis is delayed.

Based on these findings, we conclude that Tenecteplase is not only a safe thrombolytic agent but also maintains considerable effectiveness when administered beyond its standard therapeutic window.

6. Conclusion

In our study the demographic characteristics of the study population exhibited a marked preponderance of male patients (81%), and majority of patients were predominantly within the age group of 40-60 years with a mean age of 52.67 ± 13.39 . Our study concludes 40.4% patients had a well-documented history of smoking and alcohol consumption and approximately 50% of the patients presented without any concomitant diseases, whereas hypertension (22.7%) emerged as the most prevalent comorbidity among those affected. Furthermore, anterior wall myocardial infarction (AWMI) constituted the most frequent clinical presentation (55.3%), and the majority of patients (86.5%) were classified as Killip Class I, indicative of early-stage heart failure with minimal hemodynamic compromise. Our study revealed that tenecteplase had exhibited a pronounced and sustained efficacy in achieving coronary reperfusion, even when administered after the standard window period following the onset of ischemic symptoms.

Finally, our study concludes that Tenecteplase had shown maximum efficacy and favourable safety profile characterized by minimal adverse effects, thereby warranting Tenecteplase incorporation into emergency medical kits, particularly in resource-constrained or non-percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI)-capable settings.

This strategic inclusion would facilitate timely thrombolysis, thereby enhancing survival rates among patients with ST-elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) and effectively bridging the therapeutic gap in settings where immediate catheterization is not readily available. Finally, our study robustly supports the utilization of Tenecteplase as a frontline thrombolytic agent in pharmacoinvasive management strategies for acute myocardial infarction, to optimize better patient outcomes.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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